

Management Training Program and Leadership Mental Development for Field Staff of PT Intan Pertiwi Industri

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ABSTRACT

Management Training and Leadership Mental Coaching Program at PT INTIWI aims to enhance managerial skills and the mental well-being of field personnel. Against the backdrop of understanding the complexity of fieldwork and the increasingly dynamic market demands, this program is designed to cultivate outstanding field leaders. Training methods involve discipline training, case-based training, pre-tests, and post-tests. Evaluation is conducted through pre-tests and post-tests, as well as participant feedback and field performance monitoring. The program is expected to have a positive impact, such as increased productivity, job satisfaction, and a reduction in stress levels. The success of this program will create a more balanced work environment and contribute to the strategic goals achievement of PT INTIWI.

INTRODUCTION

The management training and mental leadership development program for field staff is a strategic initiative designed to improve managerial skills and strengthen mental leadership aspects in field staff. As the world of work becomes increasingly dynamic and complex (Ebrahim, 2023; Putranti, 2020), concrete efforts are needed to ensure that field staff have the necessary skills and leadership to overcome emerging challenges. The rationale for this program can be found in the understanding of the important role that field workers play in the overall operations of an organization. Field personnel are often on the frontline, directly interacting with customers or carrying out field tasks that require quick decisions and good managerial skills (Haryanto & Budi, 2020). Therefore, it is necessary to invest in the development of management skills and mental leadership development at the field level.

Management skills include the planning, organizing, supervising, and controlling abilities needed to ensure that field tasks are carried out efficiently and effectively (Latief et al., 2019). Meanwhile, mental leadership coaching (Sancoko et al., 2023; Malik et al., 2023) aims to strengthen mental resilience, creativity, and decision-making capabilities in field leaders, so that they can better deal with pressures and challenges. The program also emerged in response to the rapidly changing business environment, including technological advances, globalization, and changing customer needs. Field personnel need to constantly evolve and adapt in order to remain relevant in the face of these changes. Management training provides a solid foundation for understanding managerial concepts and their application in a field context.

In addition, the mental aspect of leadership is becoming increasingly important due to increasingly complex job demands and mounting pressures. This mental coaching covers aspects such as stress management, emotional intelligence, and mental resilience that can help field leaders face challenges with a positive and productive attitude. The implementation of this program will not only benefit the individual, but will also improve the overall performance of the organization. Field leaders who have strong management skills and good mental resilience can be a catalyst for positive change in their teams, motivate team members, and increase productivity.

PT Intan Pertiwi Industri (INTIWI) was established in 1976 and has been producing welding wire since 1977. Since then INTIWI production has technically cooperated with Kobe Steel, Ltd. Japan. PT INTIWI is one of the companies in the area under the guidance of the 052/Wijayakrama Resort Command (Korem 052/Wijayakrama) and the 0506 Tangerang Military District Command (Kodim 0506/Tangerang). Basically, community empowerment is one of the goals of the TNI (Indonesian National Army) which reflects the role of the TNI as an integral part of society. This concept shows that the TNI does not only focus on military tasks, but also has the responsibility to contribute to the development and welfare of society. Community empowerment is a strategic foundation in establishing a harmonious relationship between the TNI and the community.

That is why collaboration between academia, industry and government emerged, which in this case involved the Asmi Institute of Business and Multimedia, PT INTIWI and Korem 052/Wkr.

METHODS

The implementation of management training programs and mental leadership coaching can involve a series of structured and result-oriented methods. This Training Management Program and Mental Leadership Development activity was carried out for 8 meetings every Saturday and Sunday from September 10, 2022 to October 2, 2022. The place used for the implementation of the Training Management Program and Mental Leadership Development activities is at PT Intan Pertiwi Industri which is located at Jl. Pembangunan I No.32, RT.005 / RW.004, Batusari, Kec. Batuceper, Tangerang City, Banten 15121. The training implementation mechanism consists of: 1) Training on State Defense, UN and discipline, Unity in Diversity; 2) Management Seminar; 3) Pre-test and Post-test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Field personnel are the spearhead in maintaining service quality and business sustainability. Hence, there is a need for commitment to empower and enhance the capacity of field personnel through a comprehensive training program. An understanding of the complexity of field work, work pressure, and the need for strong management skills are the basis for the development of this program. The implementation of this training consists of 3 (three) core activities, namely:

State Defense and Marching (Discipline Physical Endurance and Mental Fighting)

The values of state defense must be better understood in its application in the life of the people of the nation and state, among others: Love for the Country, Awareness of Nation and State, Pancasila, Willing to sacrifice for the Nation and State. Have the ability to defend the country: The competencies expected after studying the material of awareness of the nation and state are that the trainees are able to understand respect for state symbols, obedience to laws and regulations, fostering harmony and maintaining national unity.

Figure 1. Implementation of the United Nations and State Defense (Discipline Physical Endurance and Mental Fighting)

Marching is a form of physical exercise that is needed to instill habits in the formation of a disciplined character. The purpose of marching training that needs to be known by trainees, aims to foster a sense of unity, namely a sense of fate and solidarity and the bonds that are established are needed to carry out tasks. Fostering an attitude of discipline, which means prioritizing the interests of the task over their own interests. Fostering a sense of responsibility, which is the courage to act, take risks that are favorable to the task, and not take actions that can harm or pose a risk to himself and the company.

Management Training

Understanding management includes material on management functions (Planning, Organizing, Actuating, Controlling). The function of the company / corporation, the influence of changes in the internal and external environment on the company, the division of time tasks, levels / levels in management. By understanding the management process in the company, participants are expected to be able to carry out planning tasks to evaluation and improvement to support the achievement of company goals.

Figure 2. Delivery of Company Management Material

Pre-test and Post-test Activities

Pre-test and post-test activities in training have an important purpose to measure the level of understanding and development of participants before and after attending the training. Comparison of pre-test and post-test results helps in evaluating the overall effectiveness of the training. If participants show significant improvement in the post-test results, it indicates that the training objectives have been achieved.

Figure 3. Pre-test and Post-test Implementation

The post-test can also assist in identifying whether there is a need for further training or upskilling in the future. If there are gaps in knowledge or skills, training providers can design additional training programs.

The Management Training and Mental Leadership Development Program at PT INTIWI reflects the company's positive response to the need to improve the competence and welfare of field personnel. Against a backdrop of understanding the complexity of field work and evolving market demands, PT INTIWI recognizes that investment in management skills development and leadership mentoring is key to improving field force performance and ensuring successful operational sustainability (Salistia et al, 2023; Putri et al, 2022; Fachriansyah & Wulandari, 2022). One of the main focuses of this program is to improve the managerial skills of the field force. In a competitive business world, strong managerial skills are crucial to deal with various challenges and work dynamics. Through interactive workshops and disciplinary training, program participants can gain an in-depth understanding of management concepts including planning, organizing, supervising, and controlling field tasks.

Not only that, the program also incorporates case-based training, which allows participants to encounter real situations and apply the concepts they have learned in a practical context. As such, participants can develop quick and precise decision-making skills, which are essential in field work that often faces urgent challenges. In addition to management aspects, the program places special emphasis on mental coaching and leadership development. Understanding that mental wellbeing greatly affects performance and productivity, PT INTIWI engages participants in personal counseling and coaching sessions. This aims to help them manage stress, increase mental resilience, and build a strong leadership foundation.

As part of the holistic program design, PT INTIWI also implements a pre-test and post-test. The pre-test is conducted prior to the commencement of the training to assess participants' initial knowledge and gain insight into areas where they require improvement. Meanwhile, a post-test is conducted after the training to assess the extent to which participants have understood and applied the concepts taught.

Program evaluation is not only limited to written exams, but also includes participant feedback and field performance monitoring (Sari & Hamdi, 2021). Through this approach, PT INTIWI can obtain more information about the effectiveness of the program, its impact on the psychological well-being of field workers, and their ability to deal with situations in the field.

The success of this program is measured by a number of performance indicators. Increased productivity is one of the key measures of success, with field workers expected to apply their new management skills to improve efficiency in carrying out their daily tasks. Job satisfaction is also expected to increase along with the improved skills and understanding gained from the program. In addition, the program is expected to reduce stress levels among field personnel. Through the mental coaching training, participants will be equipped with strategies to cope with pressures and challenges that may arise in field work. This is expected to create a more balanced work environment and support their mental well-being. The success of the program can also be seen from the leadership development of the participants. With a focus on leadership development, PT INTIWI hopes this program can create excellent field leaders, able to motivate teams, and make a positive contribution to the company's work culture.

In the overall picture, the Management Training and Mental Leadership Development Program at PT INTIWI is not just a skills development effort, but also an investment in the welfare and career advancement of field personnel. With a combination of diverse training methods and a holistic approach, this program is expected to form field leaders who are competent, resilient, and able to face dynamic changes in the world of work. The success of this program will create a positive impact not only on individual participants, but also on the overall performance and organizational culture of PT INTIWI.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results obtained from the implementation of training activities are 1) PT Intan Pertiwi Industri field workers who were selected as training participants participated well in the Training Management Program and Mental Leadership Development activities, 2) The percentage of attendance of participants is 100%, which means that participants have carried out their training obligations seriously, 3) Participants were trained by instructors who are experts in Company Managerial, and 4) Participants received training certificates after attending training and posttest/end-of-training test. The management training program and mental leadership development at PT INTIWI reflect the company's commitment to advancing the welfare and progress of field workers.

With good design and active participant involvement, this program is expected to create positive changes in work culture and individual performance, as well as contribute to the achievement of overall company goals.

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